

Volumetric absorptive microsampling and conductive vial electromembrane extraction for the analysis of pharmaceuticals in whole blood

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ABSTRACT

Volumetric absorptive microsampling (VAMS) enables accurate collection of low blood volumes, independent of hematocrit. Electromembrane extraction (EME) is a sustainable sample clean-up technique; however, its wider applicability to extract analytes directly from VAMS tips remains unexplored. This study aimed to evaluate applicability of the first commercially available conductive vial EME device (with 2-nitrophenyl octyl ether as liquid membrane) for isolating 41 basic pharmaceuticals (log P 2–6) from 10 μ L of blood on VAMS tips. The following extraction parameters were optimized: donor solution composition and volume, conductive vials size, applied voltage, extraction time and agitation speed. It was found that: 1/large conductive vials (600 μ L) and 300 μ L of donor solution provide higher process efficiency and reproducibility compared to smaller vials (200 μ L) or larger donor solution volumes; 2/methanol in donor solution improve reproducibility and 3/sonication of VAMS tips in donor solution within a conductive vial prior to extraction enhances process efficiency. The EME protocol, followed by UHPLC-MS/MS analysis, was evaluated for process efficiency, linearity (1–1000 ng/mL), precision, and accuracy. Eleven analytes met most of the predefined acceptance criteria: process efficiencies 34.9–65.8 %, linearity (R^2) 0.9933–0.9995, accuracy 85.9–111.1 % and precision 1.4–13.3 % RSD. The extraction was not impacted by hematocrit variation. EME demonstrated superior reproducibility and reduced matrix effects when compared to conventional VAMS tips treatment. This study confirms the reliability of a commercial conductive vial EME device for isolating basic pharmaceuticals from whole blood on VAMS tips, highlighting its potential for routine bioanalytical applications.

1. Introduction

Monitoring of the concentration-time profile of exogenous compounds in biological fluids is essential for various pharmacological and toxicological studies in both non-clinical and clinical settings, including therapeutic drug monitoring (TDM). This allows the correlation of drug concentrations in the body with pharmacological/toxicological effects, supports personalized medicine, helps prevent drug interactions in polypharmacy, and provides insights into patient compliance [1].

Blood is conventionally collected using traditional intravascular

sampling, which has several limitations: the process is invasive, often painful, and requires a relatively large sample volume (typically over 1 mL). Additionally, blood collection must be carried out by trained personnel, necessitating a visit to a healthcare facility, which causes patient discomfort. Most whole blood samples are processed into plasma or serum before analysis, which adds to the cost and can delay laboratory workflows. Moreover, wet plasma/serum samples require cold-chain storage and transport to prevent degradation [2,3].

Microsampling has emerged as a promising alternative, overcoming many of these limitations. It involves the collection of a small volume

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($\leq 50 \mu\text{L}$) of capillary blood in a minimally invasive manner, allowing for home collection without needing medical personnel. In the traditional microsampling technique, dried blood spot (DBS), a drop of whole blood from a finger or heel prick is applied on filter paper, which is then dried and sent for analysis. The dried matrix enhances analyte stability and simplifies both storage and transport. However, variations in hematocrit (HCT) levels can affect the results of DBS-based assays, potentially leading to incorrect analyte quantification [4].

Volumetric absorptive microsampling (VAMS), exemplified as the Mitra® device, offers a solution to mitigate the impact of HCT on assay results while preserving the benefits of DBS. It consists of a plastic holder with a hydrophilic polymeric tip that absorbs a defined volume of whole blood (10, 20, or 30 μL) regardless of the blood hematocrit. Analytes are typically extracted from VAMS tips either directly into an organic solvent or initially into an aqueous solution, followed by protein precipitation using an organic solvent. In both cases, ultrasound-assisted extraction or vigorous mixing is commonly employed [5]. Despite its potential, treating VAMS tips with microextraction methods has been rarely explored, though it holds promise to multiply the benefits of microsampling by applying practical, environmentally friendly sample cleanup.

Currently, various microextraction techniques have been described for the extraction of basic pharmaceuticals [6–9]. However, to date, only two studies have explored the potential of a microextraction specifically for treating VAMS tips. Parallel artificial liquid membrane extraction (PALME) has been employed to extract selected drugs of abuse from whole blood absorbed onto VAMS tips [10] and electromembrane extraction (EME) in a 96-well laboratory built device showed its ability to isolate doxorubicin and its metabolite from the same sample [11]. Importantly, both studies highlighted the potential of these microextraction techniques for VAMS tips treatment, but they focus on individual analytes, leaving broader applicability unexplored. Hence, further studies are desired to confirm the reliability of EME for the isolation of a broader spectrum of analytes from whole blood absorbed onto VAMS tips. Additionally, both previous studies utilized laboratory built 96-well equipment, which may present challenges in making the process more accessible to a wider range of users and complicates the transferability of the method between laboratories. In this context, introduction of the first commercially available device utilizing conductive vials represents significant improvement. To date, the practical utility of the conductive vial EME device has been only rarely studied [12,13] and its utilization for processing of biological microsamples, including whole blood on VAMS tips is still missing. The commercial EME device employs conductive vials instead of 96-well plate which bring several mechanical and practical aspects for method development that may affect extraction performance. Therefore, the reliability of the commercially available microextraction device for VAMS tips treatment requires separate study.

The current study aims at the development of a generic EME method for isolating model basic pharmaceuticals (41 analytes in log P 2–6) from whole blood absorbed onto VAMS tips using commercially available conductive vial EME equipment. Specifically, this study for the first time 1) summarizes how optimization of the main EME parameters affects the extraction of the broader range of pharmaceuticals from VAMS-collected whole blood, 2) assesses the suitability of commercially available conductive vial EME equipment for direct VAMS tips processing, and 3) evaluates the possibility of establishing generic conditions for extraction of pharmaceuticals from whole blood microsamples collected by VAMS.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Chemicals and materials

Acetonitrile (LC-MS grade), methanol (LC-MS grade) and 2-nitrophenyl octyl ether (NPOE) were purchased from Sigma-Aldrich (St.

Louis, MO, USA). Formic acid (LC-MS grade) was obtained from VWR (Radnor, PA, USA). Ultrapure water was prepared with a Milipak® (0.22 μm filter) Milli-Q water purification system (Molsheim, France). Mitra® devices (10 μL) were obtained from Trajan Scientific Europe Ltd (Milton Keynes, United Kingdom). Circular polypropylene membranes (type PP2E, thickness of 110 μm , diameter of 9 mm) were from Extraction Technologies Norway (Ski, Norway). Forty-one different pharmaceuticals (log P from 2 to 6), used as model analytes (Supplementary material – Table S1) were all obtained from Sigma Aldrich (St. Louis, MO, USA).

2.2. Preparation of solutions

Stock solutions for all 41 pharmaceuticals (1.0–9.0 mg/mL) were prepared individually by dissolution of an appropriate amount of each substance in methanol, DMSO, or water. A combined solution of all 41 compounds (5 $\mu\text{g/mL}$) was then prepared by mixing the appropriate amount of each stock solution and water, divided into aliquots, and stored at -28°C . Working solutions for evaluation experiments (0.1–1 $\mu\text{g/mL}$) were prepared from the combined solution by appropriate dilution with water.

2.3. Preparation of standard, calibration, and QC whole blood samples

Fresh drug-free human whole blood with EDTA as anticoagulant (obtained from a healthy volunteer) was used for preparation of spiked samples for method development and evaluation. Whole blood was spiked with an appropriate amount of combined solution of analytes and incubated at 37°C for 15 min, while gently shaken at 350 RPM (Thermomixer comfort 1.5 ml, Eppendorf, Germany), to establish an equilibrium in the concentrations of the analytes between plasma and blood cells. After incubation, blood was absorbed onto VAMS tips according to the recommendations [5] and dried for 2 h. Dried blood samples were stored in air-tight bags in a refrigerator and analyzed within 48 h.

2.4. Methodology

A graphical overview of the entire methodology illustrates the sequential steps of the workflow, from development through evaluation and comparison of EME to conventional VAMS tip treatment, as shown in Fig. 1.

2.5. Electromembrane extraction

Electromembrane extraction was performed with a commercially available device (ETN-12 EME, Extraction Technologies Norway AS, Ski, Norway). Two sizes of conductive vials were used. Small vials (200 μL total volume) were employed for the acceptor phase, while either small or large vials (600 μL total volume) were tested for the donor phase. A circular porous polypropylene membrane (type PP2E, thickness of 110 μm , diameter of 9 mm) was used as the support for an organic solvent, and it was placed between vials, held by support membrane unit. Before extraction, VAMS tips were placed into the donor vial and donor solvent was added. Then the support membrane was placed into a support membrane unit, screwed at the vial and 10 μL of NPOE was deposited onto the membrane. This unit with donor vial was then screwed on the top of the acceptor vial containing 100 μL of 100 mM formic acid (the acceptor solvent). Connected conductive vials were placed into the EME device and voltage was applied while shaking. Extraction was controlled by software (ETN Extractor v1.0.1). Photographs of the VAMS device and the commercial EME device are provided in the Supplementary material (Fig. S1). The following EME conditions were used during method optimization: composition of the donor solvent (250 mM formic acid with/without addition of methanol 12.5 %), different volumes of the donor solvent (300 and 450 μL), different applied voltage (50 and 100 V), agitation speed (900 and 1100 RPM) and time of extraction (15,

Fig. 1. A graphical representation of the methodology.

30 and 45 min). Finally, the impact of VAMS tip sonication in a donor solvent before extraction (0, 15 and 30 min) was evaluated. Each optimization experiment was performed in triplicate and data were evaluated for process efficiency (PE) calculated according to equation (1) and reproducibility expressed as RSD.

$$PE = \frac{\text{Area (sample)}}{\text{Area (standard)}} * 100 \quad (1)$$

Area (sample) is an area of each analyte in the sample after extraction of spiked whole blood from VAMS tip and Area (standard) represents the area of each analyte in a standard solution prepared by spiking 100 mM formic acid with the analytes at the corresponding concentration.

The final extraction protocol was evaluated for matrix effects (ME), which were calculated according to equation (2).

$$ME = \frac{\text{Area (post-spiked sample)}}{\text{Area (standard)}} * 100 \quad (2)$$

Area (post-spiked sample) is an area of each analyte in the spiked acceptor solution after extraction of blank (drug-free) blood from VAMS tips and Area (standard) represents the area of each analyte in a standard solution prepared by spiking 100 mM formic acid with the analytes at the corresponding concentration.

2.6. Conventional VAMS tips treatment

Direct extraction of the pharmaceuticals from whole blood absorbed onto VAMS tips into an organic solvent was performed for comparison. A VAMS tip was placed into a 1.5 mL Eppendorf tube, followed by the addition of 200 μ L of methanol. The samples were then sonicated for 30 min, centrifuged (1050 RPM, 4 $^{\circ}$ C, 10 min), and the supernatant was collected for the analysis. Process efficiency and matrix effects were calculated in the same manner as for EME with the exception of using methanol in the standard solution.

2.7. UHPLC-MS/MS method

The analysis was performed with an Agilent 1290 Infinity II UHPLC system (Agilent Technologies, Santa Clara, CA, USA) coupled with mass spectrometric detection (Agilent 6495 LC/TQ, Agilent Technologies). The chromatographic and detection conditions were adopted from a previously established method [13].

Briefly, an Eclipse Plus C18 column (2.1 mm \times 50 mm, 1.8 μ m, Agilent Technologies) maintained at 40 $^{\circ}$ C was used for the separation. Mobile phases A and B consisted of ultrapure water and acetonitrile in 95:5 and 5:95 (v/v) ratios, respectively, both containing 0.1 % formic acid. The following gradient was used: 0.00–1.00 (0 % B), 1.01–6.00 (0–53 % B), 6.01–7.00 (75 % B), 7.01–7.50 (100 % B), 7.51–9.00 (0 % B). The mobile phase flow rate was maintained at 0.4 mL/min from 0.00 to 7.00 min, increased to 0.7 mL/min between 7.01 and 8.50 min, and then returned to 0.4 mL/min from 8.51 to 9.00 min. The injection volume was 5.0 μ L.

The MS instrument utilized electrospray ionization in a positive ion mode with 3 kV as a capillary voltage with a gas temperature set to 200 $^{\circ}$ C, operated in dynamic MRM mode, with a cycle time of 300 ms.

Additional detection parameters can be found in the Supplementary material (Table S1).

2.8. Method evaluation

Although the method was not fully validated, specific validation parameters were selected to evaluate the reliability of the EME procedure with UHPLC-MS/MS analysis to assay all tested pharmaceuticals from whole blood absorbed onto VAMS tips: linearity, process efficiency, accuracy and precision. Acceptance criteria for this evaluation were based on FDA and EMA bioanalytical method validation guidelines [14,15] and the previous EME study (process efficiency) [13]. The method was considered applicable for the analysis of the specific analyte if the following conditions were fulfilled: process efficiency (>40 %), linearity ($R^2 > 0.99$), accuracy (85–115 %) and precision (<15 % RSD). The effect of various hematocrit was further examined for the analytes that met these criteria. The whole blood samples used for evaluation experiments were prepared as described above (Section 2.3).

Linearity was tested using calibration whole blood samples at 6 concentration levels of the analytes (1, 10, 50, 100, 500 and 1000 ng/mL) where the concentration of 1 ng/mL represents a lower limit of quantification (LLOQ), three independent samples were prepared for each level. Process efficiency was tested at a concentration of 100 ng/mL ($n = 4$) and accuracy and precision (both, $n = 4$) were verified at 2 concentration levels (low: 100 ng/mL and high: 500 ng/mL).

Fresh whole blood of three different hematocrit levels was prepared as follows to examine an impact of this parameter on assay results. Whole blood was centrifuged (750 G, 10 min, 4 $^{\circ}$ C) to separate plasma and blood cells. Then, plasma was mixed with blood cells in different portions to prepare samples of different HCT values (30 %, 40 % and 50 % HCT, each level, $n = 3$). These blood samples were then spiked with the analytes (100 ng/mL), loaded onto VAMS tips and after drying, they were extracted using an optimized EME procedure. The analytes concentrations obtained in blood samples of different HCT levels were compared.

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Development and optimization of electromembrane extraction

The development of a generic EME method for VAMS tips treatment was built on the generic method B1 previously reported for extracting various pharmaceuticals from plasma [13]. In this study, we focused on 41 pharmaceuticals (see Supplementary material – Table S1) with log P values ranging from 2 to 6, which fall within the extraction window of 2-nitrophenyl octyl ether (NPOE) – the solvent used in the B1 generic method. This solvent enabled efficient extraction of the selected analytes from plasma. However, our previous experiments clearly showed that the character of the biological matrix affects the extraction [16,17]. Moreover, in the case of VAMS tips, the extraction effectiveness is additionally influenced by the presence of a solid polymer-based tip. NPOE as a SLM and 100 mM formic acid as an acceptor solution remained from the plasma treatment protocol, while the other extraction conditions were optimized to suit the extraction of the pharmaceuticals from 10 μ L of whole blood absorbed onto VAMS tips.

3.1.1. Composition and volume of donor solution, size of conductive vials

The composition and the volume of the donor solution were optimized, as they are supposed to be critical in the achievement of the effective desorption of analytes from whole blood absorbed onto VAMS tips. Initially, 250 mM formic acid was tested, following the recommended conditions for extraction of the analytes for plasma using the generic method B1 [13]. Next, the solvent was enriched with methanol (12.5 %) to examine the possible improvement of the desorption process. This amount reflects the risk of SLM leakage from the membrane that may occur in higher methanol content [18].

Two sizes of conductive vials – small and large (total volume of 200 and 600 μL , respectively) – filled with either 100 or 300 μL of the donor solution were examined and the process efficiency and reproducibility of extractions were compared. Poor within-extraction reproducibility, demonstrated by high standard deviations (SD), was obtained for most analytes using small vials with 100 μL of 250 mM formic acid as the donor solution – see supplementary material (Fig. S2a). Contrary, extraction using large conductive vials with 300 μL of donor solution improved reproducibility across all analytes. This could be attributed to the limited space within the small vial, which likely hindered effective convection and desorption of the analytes from whole blood absorbed onto solid polymer of the VAMS tip. Furthermore, enrichment of the donor solution with methanol improved reproducibility when compared to the same donor solvent without methanol (Fig. 2a and b and Figure S2b). Further increase of the volume of donor solvent (from 300 μL to 450 μL), did not improve process efficiency and reproducibility (data not shown). The highest process efficiency along with the lowest RSDs between extractions were achieved using 300 μL of 250 mM formic acid with 12.5 % methanol as the donor solvent.

3.1.2. Optimization of other EME conditions

After optimizing the conductive vial size, volume, and composition of the donor solution, we aimed at increasing process efficiency, which had been significantly lower for most analytes than in the extraction from plasma [13]. In all above-mentioned experiments, the applied voltage was set to 50 V and the extraction time was 30 min, similarly to the generic B1 method. At first, the applied voltage was increased to 100 V, but this modification resulted in poor reproducibility (Supplementary material – Fig. S3).

Next, three different extraction times – 15, 30, and 45 min – were tested. Although this parameter had only a minor effect on process efficiency, both short (15 min) and long (45 min) extraction times led to reduced reproducibility. This is evidenced by the RSD values for the analytes with process efficiency higher than 40 % (Fig. 3). The reproducibility of analytes with process efficiency below 40 % are not presented, as low process efficiencies are often associated with high RSDs, offering limited explanatory value [13]. These results suggested that 15 min is insufficient time for the analytes to pass through the membrane

Fig. 3. Optimization of extraction time. Results are presented as process efficiency RSDs (%), $n = 3$) calculated for each analyte whose process efficiency was ≥ 40 %.

and 45 min likely compromises membrane stability, as the VAMS tip – a solid object – repeatedly contacts the membrane during extraction.

Finally, higher agitation speed (1100 RPM) was tested to evaluate whether faster shaking could enhance extraction process efficiencies. The results indicated that increasing the agitation speed had only a minor impact on process efficiency (mean increase in process efficiency = 8 %). However, due to concerns about membrane stability previously described in 96-well EME format [11], we opted to use 900 RPM.

3.1.3. Effect of VAMS tips sonication prior to EME

As the efforts to enhance process efficiency via modification of common EME conditions failed, sonication of the VAMS tips in the donor solution before the extraction was examined, as it could facilitate the analytes' desorption. Fifteen- and 30-min sonication improved process efficiency for 24 and 30 of 41 analytes (with mean process efficiency increase 3.6 % and 14 %), respectively, while the process efficiency of the remaining analytes either stayed the same or slightly decreased. The sonication step likely facilitated the desorption of several analytes from the polymer of VAMS tips into the donor solution. Since the majority of tested analytes showed improvement, a 30-min sonication in conductive vials before EME extraction was used in evaluation experiments.

3.2. Method evaluation

The following EME parameters were selected as optimal for isolation of most analytes from whole blood absorbed onto VAMS tips: The VAMS tips in the large conductive donor vials were immersed in 300 μL of 250 mM formic acid enriched with methanol (12.5 %). The vial was sealed

Fig. 2. Optimization of donor solvent composition in large conductive donor vials with 300 μL of 250 mM formic acid (a) and 250 mM formic acid with 12.5 % methanol (b). Results are presented as a mean process efficiency \pm SD ($n = 3$).

with a cap and subjected to sonication for 30 min. Following this, the cap was replaced with a unit containing a support membrane, onto which 10 μL of NPOE was carefully applied. The donor vial, now equipped with the supported membrane, was then securely screwed onto the top of a small conductive acceptor vial containing 100 μL of 100 mM formic acid. Connected conductive vials were placed into the EME device, closed with the lid with electrodes, 50 V was applied, and extraction was performed for 30 min at 900 RPM.

This general EME protocol, followed by UHPLC-MS/MS assay was evaluated for the determination of all analytes from whole blood absorbed onto VAMS tips by examining selected parameters (process efficiency, linearity, accuracy, and precision). The corresponding data are presented in the supplementary material (Table S2). Ten tested analytes fulfilled all evaluation criteria, which were based on the FDA and EMA bioanalytical method validation guidelines [14,15] and considering typical EME process efficiency [13]: process efficiency (>40 %), linearity ($R^2 > 0.99$), accuracy (85–115 %) and precision (RSD <15 %). Additionally, one compound (clomipramine) met most parameters and exhibited only slightly lower process efficiency (35 %). The evaluation data for these eleven analytes are presented in Table 1.

Sufficient linearity across the concentration range (1–1000 ng/mL) was demonstrated by an R^2 value ≥ 0.993 for all eleven analytes. Within the scope of this methodological framework, the lowest concentration level assessed for linearity is taken to represent the LLOQ. The process efficiency ranged from 34.9 to 65.8 %, while precision, expressed as RSD, was <13.3 % at both low and high concentration levels. Accuracy was within 85.9–111.1 % for both concentration levels (Table 1). Additionally, the effect of hematocrit (HCT) on the assay results was evaluated. No significant differences in detector response were observed for any of the eleven analytes across the tested HCT levels (30 %, 40 % and 50 %), the typical human range [19]. This proves that our extraction protocol provides consistent results for these eleven pharmaceuticals, independent of blood HCT (Fig. 4).

Compared to the VAMS tips treatment using the laboratory built 96-well format used in previous studies [10,11], the conductive vial EME device enhances analyte desorption by enabling ultrasound application prior to extraction. Moreover, because of its different structural design, it prevents the occasional dislodging of the liquid membrane support that can occur in higher intensity of shaking in the 96-well format [11].

The developed extraction procedure is versatile with highly purifying power and could be also coupled with other analytical techniques, such as UHPLC-UV/VIS, which are commonly available in most laboratories. However, compared to MS detection, the linearity concentration range would need to be adjusted when using UV/VIS detection.

Table 1

Results of evaluation for selected analytes. Linearity was verified within the concentration range of 1–1000 ng/mL using 6 concentration levels ($n = 3$), process efficiency (PE) was tested at a concentration 100 ng/mL ($n = 4$), precision and accuracy at two concentration levels – 100 ng/mL and 500 ng/mL ($n = 4$). Log P values were obtained from Ref. [20].

Analyte	log P	Linearity (R^2)	PE (%)	Precision (RSD %)		Accuracy (%)	
				100	500	100	500
Noscapine	2.58	0.9976	48.4	2.7	7.1	95.7	105.0
Diltiazem	2.73	0.9977	53.5	1.4	8.6	94.9	103.7
Papaverine	3.08	0.9988	58.0	11.4	7.1	93.6	103.5
Haloperidol	3.66	0.9946	47.6	10.1	6.0	95.8	108.8
Mianserin	3.83	0.9992	43.6	7.7	6.8	92.7	99.3
Doxepin	3.84	0.9993	45.3	4.4	7.9	85.9	99.3
Fluoxetine	4.17	0.9995	48.0	1.6	9.9	90.4	99.6
Nortriptyline	4.43	0.9933	42.8	7.6	13.3	87.0	111.1
DBDAP ^a	4.60	0.9994	62.1	4.9	3.7	87.5	101.5
Loperamide	4.77	0.9976	65.8	5.0	9.3	97.3	107.9
Clomipramine	4.88	0.9989	34.9	6.8	6.7	85.9	100.6

^a DBDAP = 2,6-di-*tert*-butyl-4-(dimethylaminomethyl)phenol.

Fig. 4. Effect of various hematocrits on the extraction of selected analytes. Comparison of analytes response assayed in whole blood of 30 %, 40 % or 50 % HCT spiked at the concentration of 100 ng/mL and absorbed onto VAMS tips. The results are expressed as the mean response assayed from four independent measurements \pm SD. Statistical analysis was performed in GraphPad Prism 10.4.1 using One-way ANOVA with Bonferroni's multiple comparison test. The level of significance was set on $p \leq 0.05$. ns – not significant. DBDAP = 2,6-di-*tert*-butyl-4-(dimethylaminomethyl)phenol.

3.3. Comparison of electromembrane extraction to conventional VAMS tips treatment

The optimized EME protocol for isolating the analytes from whole blood absorbed onto VAMS tips was compared to direct ultrasound-assisted extraction with methanol. This comparison covers process efficiencies and matrix effects, specifically focused on eleven pharmaceuticals that fulfilled evaluation criteria. The conventional extraction method yielded process efficiencies of the analytes within the range of 31–79 % (Table S3), which was, for most analytes, higher compared to EME (35–58 %). However, EME is not usually an exhaustive extraction technique and thus process efficiencies higher than 40 % are considered as sufficient [12,13]. In contrast, EME demonstrated significantly lower matrix effects due to its superior purification capabilities (Fig. 5). These results are in line with previously published work [11]. Moreover, EME required substantially less organic solvent than conventional sample preparation methods, making it a more environmentally friendly

Fig. 5. Comparison of matrix effects for optimized EME protocol and conventional extraction method. The results are expressed as the mean matrix effects obtained from 4 individual experiments \pm SD. DBDAP = 2,6-di-*tert*-butyl-4-(dimethylaminomethyl)phenol.

approach, as consistently demonstrated in previous studies [11,21,22]. Additionally, the method's sustainability for selected analytes was assessed using the RGB 12 algorithm, following the approach outlined in previously published literature [23,24]. The results indicate that EME is a greener technique. However, due to the requirement for a specific EME extraction device, the conventional extraction using methanol has slightly higher score according to the blue indicator, expressing the practical side. (Supplementary Material – Fig. S4).

4. Conclusion

This work examines, for the first time, the capability of a commercial EME device to directly isolate various pharmaceuticals (log P from 2 to 6) from whole blood microsamples absorbed onto VAMS tips. Our experiments underline the importance of selecting the appropriate conductive vial size and volume of donor solution to achieve high extraction performance. They revealed that using 600 μ L conductive vials along with 300 μ L of donor solvent provided higher process efficiency and reproducibility for most tested analytes compared to smaller conductive vials (maximum volume of 200 μ L) or larger volumes of donor solvent. The latter setups likely restrict the movement of the VAMS tip inside the vials, which seems to be important for effective desorption. It was found that the addition of methanol (12.5%) to the donor phase improves reproducibility. Furthermore, sonication of VAMS tips immersed in the donor solution within a conductive vial prior to extraction enhances process efficiency, as it likely facilitates the desorption of whole blood from the solid VAMS tip into the donor solution. After optimizing the extraction protocol, selected validation parameters (process efficiency, linearity, precision, and accuracy) were evaluated for EME followed by UHPLC-MS/MS assay for all 41 analytes. Eleven of the analytes met the majority of the acceptance criteria, and their assay was unaffected by various HCT levels. Even though the general conditions optimal for all 41 tested pharmaceuticals were not established, it was proven that a commercially available EME device (ETN-12 EME) can be used for direct processing of VAMS tips containing whole blood microsamples. This study presents an extraction protocol that can serve as a starting point for further advanced optimization of the extraction of basic pharmaceuticals with log P 2–6 from whole blood absorbed onto VAMS tips. Furthermore, this study contributes to understanding the positives and limitations of EME commercial devices in the isolation of the analytes from whole blood microsamples directly from the sampling device, i. e., VAMS tip.

CRediT authorship contribution statement

Adam Reguli: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Validation, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Samira Dowlatshah:** Writing – review & editing, Validation, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation. **Frederik André Hansen:** Writing – review & editing, Methodology, Conceptualization. **Petra Štěrbová-Kovářková:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Validation, Methodology, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization. **Stig Pedersen-Bjerggaard:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Validation, Supervision, Methodology, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare the following financial interests/personal relationships which may be considered as potential competing interests: Samira Dowlatshah reports financial support was provided by Extraction Technologies Norway AS. Samira Dowlatshah reports a relationship with Extraction Technologies Norway AS that includes: employment. All other authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Appendix A. Supplementary data

Supplementary data to this article can be found online at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.talanta.2025.128523>.

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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